

TWO MANGGHUER (TU, MONGUOR, MONGGHUL) WEDDING SONGS (2008) FROM MINHE COUNTY, QINGHAI PROVINCE, PR CHINA

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents two Mangghuer (Monguor, Tu) wedding songs from Minhe Hui and Tu Autonomous County, Qinghai Province, PR China. "Highland Barley Liquor" (ten lines) is sung in a mix of Mangghuer and the local Chinese dialect. "Gatehouse" (six seven-line stanzas) is sung in the local Chinese dialect. "Highland Barley Liquor" is glossed and is presented as performed in English translation and Modern Standard Chinese (MSC). "Gatehouse" is glossed and presented in English translation, local Chinese as performed, and in MSC. Collection, singers, and performance context details are given. This is the first work featuring Mangghuer wedding song lyrics as sung is glossed, translated into English and, in the case of Mangghuer lyrics, translated into English and Chinese.

KEYWORDS

China minority weddings, China wedding songs, Mangghuer (Tu, Monguor), Qinghai folk culture, Minhe County weddings, Mongolian wedding songs

INTRODUCTION

FIG 1. Minhe Hui and Tu Autonomous County, Qinghai Province, PR China.¹

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¹ An edited version of <https://tinyurl.com/f3b4cedn>, accessed 20 March 2021.

FIG 2. Mangghuer area in the south of Minhe County.¹

It was a Saturday morning in June 2008 when my friend, Mr. Deng Yulong (b. 1986), phoned and asked, "How's your Mangghuer folk music collecting going? My uncle returned home yesterday. He is famous for his songs in my home village area. What if we visit him this weekend?"

I was collecting folk songs and looking for Mangghuer singers in my home area. It was, at times, quite frustrating because most younger villagers had left home to earn money in urban areas. So, eagerly accepting Mr. Deng's invitation, I jumped out of bed, prepared my sound recorder and camera, and rushed to the Guanting Senior Middle School where he teaches.

About twenty minutes later, I was sitting behind Mr. Deng on a motorcycle, heading to Dengjia Village, located in the mountains north of the Yellow River. Around noon, about thirty minutes later, we reached Mr. Deng's home. At this time, local Mangghuer had started building houses with armored concrete. However, Mr. Deng's village houses featured traditional timber and cob wall construction, with traditional wood-carved decorations. The narrow tracks leading to and from the mountain villages made transporting modern building materials virtually impossible.

After arriving, we found that Mr. Deng's uncle was visiting his wife's parents in Xing'er Tibetan Autonomous Township. His son told us he wouldn't be back that night. Few people were in the village. That day, most adults were doing voluntary labor in the village monastery, Ziger. Mr. Deng told me

¹ An edited version of <https://tinyurl.com/p3svpu3c>, accessed 20 March 2021.

that Ziger was Tibetan for "monastery," and he didn't know the monastery's real name.¹ Later, Mr. Deng suggested we find someone at the monastery construction site to sing, but I didn't want to disturb them.

I was aware of Yindong Ghuer 'Silver Cave Valley' near Mr. Deng's village from reading *Wuyan de Niujiaohao 'The Wailing Bullhorn'* (published in 1989) written in Chinese by the Mangghuer writer, Bao Yizhi (b. 1951).² The first published literary treatment I had read focused on places and people in my home area. Yindong Ghuer was one of the locations featured in this work. I asked Mr. Deng to take me there. Elders say that it is the only place that produced coal in the Sanchuan³ Mangghuer area.⁴ According to the description in *Wuyan de Niujiaohao*, there must have been virgin forests in this area at some point in the past. However, bushes, flowers, and grass were all I saw. Such a green, lush area is rare these days in my home area. Anyway, I thought it was an ideal setting for Bao's stories.

It was twilight as we rode back to Guanting Town. Passing through Renjia Village, we saw a woman sweeping a yard in front of a small shop. No other buildings were near. After several hours of walking in Yindong Ghuer we were thirsty, so we stopped to buy drinks.

"How about having some cups of hot water?" asked the shop owner after we bought two bottles of Pepsi, "These commercial drinks can't quench your thirst. I have a solar cooker here in the yard, so I have plenty of hot water."

Ms. Zhu Lanxiang (b. 1946) was talkative. I told her the purpose of our trip and asked if she could sing Mangghuer folk songs. She laughed, "Of course! Everybody can sing Mangghuer songs! We can't sing any modern songs. We sing only the old songs."

Though she was a bit shy, she agreed to sing. It was dark and hot inside her shop, so we moved to the yard where there two or three plastic stools and one wooden chair. Ms. Zhu and I spent several minutes discussing who should sit in the chair. Ms. Zhu insisted I sit in the chair because I was a guest, while I insisted that she take the chair because she was much older than me and she would sing. She finally consented. Mr. Deng and I sat on the stools.

As soon as she started singing, I realized that she was an excellent singer. Her melodious singing flew into the valley in front of her small shop. She sang two wedding songs (including "Highland Barley Liquor,"⁵ below) and a lullaby (not presented here). Traditionally, during Mangghuer weddings in the Sanchuan Mangghuer Area, two men from the groom's home come to the bride's home at night to take her to the groom's home. Women from the bride's village sing this song to the bridetakers while offering them liquor.

¹ Ziger may be from *sgar* 'small (usually village) monastery' derived from *dmag sgar* 'camp', 'military camp'. (I thank Skal bzang nor bu for this information.)

² For more on Bao, see Stuart and Hu (1991, 1990). For a story from this collection translated from Chinese to English, see Bao (1991).

³ Sanchuan 'Three Plains' is an unofficial term used by locals for where Mangghuer live north of the Yellow River. "Sanchuan" does not appear on lists of administrative divisions. The original meaning of *chuan* is "river" in Chinese, and also refers to alluvial plains and relatively flat, low-lying places between mountains.

⁴ Before the 1980s, most Mangghuer did not use coal for cooking or heating because coal was expensive and difficult to transport from a mountain area such as Yindong Ghuer. In the 1980s, locals began using metal stoves for heating and cooking. At this time, the Mangghuer who purchased coal generally did so from the Guanting Town market for winter use, particularly during the Spring Festival period. Firewood and livestock dung were common winter fuels. In the summer, locals burned straw when cooking and boiling water. Around the year 2000, gas was introduced as a fuel in Sanchuan. Wen Yingxian was the first Wenjia Village resident to cook with bottled gas, which he purchased in nearby Danhejia Town (located in Jishishan Bao'an, Dongxiang, and Salar (Sala) Autonomous County, Linxia Hui Autonomous Prefecture, Gansu Province). Since 2010, Mangghuer families increasingly used gas as cooking fuel because it was faster and more convenient than using straw. In 2020, bottled gas could easily be purchased from Guanting Town or calling a delivery service and having it brought to the home. Wen Jinde (b. 1949) told me that very few people in the vicinity of his village (Wenjia) fetched coal from Yindong Ghuer when he was a child.

⁵ <https://bit.ly/3qZoGte>, accessed 30 January 2021.

After I finished recording, I asked if I could take her picture. She agreed and removed her scarf, explaining, "We mountain women wear scarves, which are not stylish today on the Guanting streets. Let me take it off, or people will laugh when they see my picture."

A week later, I had her photograph developed and asked Mr. Deng to give it to her the next time he went home.

FIG 3. Yindong Ghuer (2008, Wen Xiangcheng).

About two weeks later, my elder brother (Wen Yingxian, b. 1974) and I invited our paternal cousin, Wen Xuezhong (b. 1978), to my brother's home in Wenjia Village. My Brother and Wen Xuezhong drank some liquor and began singing Mangghuer wedding songs (see "Gatehouse,"¹ below).

During weddings held by my paternal clan members, Wen Yingxian and Wen Xuezhong are singing partners because of their similar voices and age. Mangghuer often spend a week or more to practice singing and rehearsing before the wedding day. However, my brother and cousins had sung together many times, so they started singing after a few cups of liquor without rehearsing.

LOCATION

Minhe Hui and Tu Autonomous County is located in Qinghai Province, PR China. The county population of 387,041 includes Han (172,269), Hui (156,546), Tu (43,585), and Tibetan (13,752), living in eight towns and fourteen townships (including Xing'er Tibetan Autonomous Township).²

¹ <https://bit.ly/2NQGJDR>, accessed 30 January 2021.

² <https://tinyurl.com/y3te7l5l>, accessed 29 January 2021.

The Mangghuer language shares typical morphosyntactic characteristics of Mongolic languages, however, phonologically, it strongly resembles Sinitic but has a stress system rather than a tone system (Slater 2003:2).

This paper presents two songs, "Highland Barley Liquor"¹ (ten lines) and "Gatehouse" (six seven-lined stanzas). "Highland Barley Liquor" is performed only by women (at weddings) and sung in a mix of Mangghuer and the local Chinese dialect. This song details how the singer made liquor from highland barley and now offers it in a porcelain cup to the bride-takers. "Highland Barley Liquor" is glossed and translated into English and Modern Standard Chinese (MSC).

"Gatehouse" is performed only by men (at weddings) in the local Chinese dialect. This song is sung by two men from the groom's clan when liquor is offered to important guests, such as the matchmaker and the groom's and bride's maternal uncles seated together at the most important banquet table. The first five stanzas of the song describe an ideal Mangghuer family - wealthy and with three sons and one daughter.² Only wealthy Mangghuer families have imposing gatehouses. The family mentioned in this song has three sons and one daughter, and all are successful - a blessing to the new family. However, this song's immediate, practical purpose is to offer liquor to main guests, so the last stanza is the most important part of the song, with these key guests described as Eight-Treasure elders 'celestial beings'. When this last stanza is sung, young men from the groom's clan approach the guests and offer liquor.

This song is glossed and presented in English translation, local Chinese as performed, and an MSC version.³

In 2020, both men and women were singing the two songs just described.

While this paper is not the first work on Mangghuer songs (e.g., see Wang and Stuart 1995a, 1995b; Wang et al. 1995; Ma 1990; Hu and Stuart 1992; Zhu and Stuart 1996; Zhu, Qi, and Stuart 1997; Qi et al. 1999), it is the only work I am familiar with that features sung wedding lyrics that are glossed and translated into English and, in the case of Mangghuer lyrics, that are glossed and translated into Chinese and English.

SONG ONE: HIGHLAND BARLEY LIQUOR

1

boghuoling-ni	andige	boghuoling-her
低处的	鸡蛋	低一些
low-GEN	egg	low-COMP

Low egg is a bit low.⁴

¹ Local Mangghuer refer to this song as Boghuolingni Andige 'Low Egg' or Moghuolingni Andige 'Round Egg'. However, it must be noted that locals often refer to a song using its first line or a few words from the first line, which may not convey the meaning of the song. Zhu Lanxiang sang using *boghuoling* 'low'. However, I heard *moghuolingni andige* by other singers. *Moghuoling* 'round' is heard in Mangghuer in mountain areas. *Boghuoling* is very similar in pronunciation to *moghuoling*. This song was commonly heard in mountain areas during weddings in about the year 2000, and later was also heard in plain areas and both *boghuoling* and *moghuoling* were used by the singers, although Mangghuer in plain areas do not use the term *moghuoling* 'round' in daily communication.

² A Mangghuer family with at least two sons and one daughter is considered a model family.

³ The orthography for Mangghuer in this paper is based on the Chinese Pinyin system following Slater (2003). I write terms sung in the local Chinese dialect in a modified Chinese Pinyin system and also in MSC Pinyin. I thank Dr. Keith Slater for his assistance in glossing the songs in this paper.

⁴ Regarding "*Boghuolingni andige boghuoling'her*," I have not observed alcohol production among the Mangghuer. However, elders I consulted explained that egg was added to liquor when it was produced locally decades ago. This is likely related to protein in egg white precipitating suspended solids, clarifying the liquor.

2

qingkuo qing-ni duruasi china-gu ge
 青稞 清的 酒 煮 做
 highland barley clear-GEN liquor boil-IMPERF do
 Boil highland barley to make clear liquor.

3

amukhang-ni kuerniege panluo-gu ge
 小米的 酒曲 搅拌进去 做
 millet-GEN yeast stir-IMPERF do
 Stir yeast made from millet into the boiled highland barley.

4

shouqingla-gu luzi-du dala-gu ge
 燃烧很旺的 炉子里 酿造 做
 blazing-IMPERF stove-DAT brew-IMPERF do
 Brew liquor on the blazing stove.

5

shazi sha-ni jiuger-du jielie-gu ge
 沙子 黄色的 酒缸里 接 做
 sand yellow-GEN liquor jar-DAT collect-IMPERF do
 Collect liquor in the sand-yellow jar.

6

dala-sang-ni kuguo duruasi muni warzhighe-ni zhongzhuer-du
 酿造的 蓝色 酒 我的 陶瓷的 酒盅里
 brew-PERF-NOMLZR clear liquor my porcelain-GEN liquor cup-DAT
 Brewed clear liquor in my porcelain cup.

7

cuguan gaga yo
 娶馆 哥哥 哟
 bridetaker older-brother PRT
 Older-Brother bridetakers,

8

muni qingkuo qing-ni dala-sang-ni yizhong-ni miaoke ya
 我的 青稞 清的 酿造的 一盅 品尝 呀
 my highland barley clear-GEN brew-PERF-NOMLZR one cup-ACC taste PRT
 Please taste one cup of liquor that I brewed from highland barley.

9

cuguan gaga-ni
 娶馆 哥哥
 bridetaker older-brother

Older-Brother bridgetakers,

10

ni	yibei-ni	durausi-ni	qi	wu	yo
这	一杯的	酒	你	喝	哟
this	one cup-GEN	liquor-ACC	you	drink	PRT

Drink this cup of liquor.

MANGGHUER

¹Boghuolingni andige boghuoling'her.

²Qingkuo qingni duruasi chinagu ge.

³Amukhangni kuerniege panluogu ge.

⁴Shouqinglagu luzidu dalagu ge.

⁵Shazi shani jiugerdu jieliege ge.

⁶Dalasangni kuguo duruasi muni warzhigheni zhongzhuerdu.

⁷Cuguan gaga yo,

⁸Muni qingkuo qingni dalasangni yizhongni miaoke ya.

⁹Cuguan gagani,

¹⁰Ni yibeini durausini qi wu yo.

ENGLISH TRANSLATION

¹Low egg is a bit low.

²Boil highland barley to make clear liquor.

³Stir yeast made from millet into the boiled highland barley.

⁴Brew liquor on the blazing stove.

⁵Collect liquor in the sand-yellow jar.

⁶Brewed clear liquor in my porcelain cup.

⁷Older-Brother bridgetakers,

⁸Please taste one cup of liquor that I brewed from highland barley.

⁹Older-Brother bridgetakers,

¹⁰Drink this cup of liquor.

MSC CHINESE TRANSLATION

¹Di chu de ji dan zai di yi dian.

²Ba feng shou de qing ke zhu shu niang jiu.

³Ba xiao mi zuo de jiu qu jiao ban jin qu.

⁴Zai xiong xiong ran shao de huo lu shang niang zao mei jiu.

⁵Niang hao de mei jiu jie dao sha huang se de jiu gang li.

⁶Qing qing de mei jiu dao jin wo tao ci de jiu zhong li.

⁷Qu guan ge ge,

⁸Qing ni pin chang yi zhong wo qin shou niang zao de mei jiu.

⁹Qu guan ge ge,

¹⁰Qing ni he xia zhe yi zhong mei jiu.

¹低处的鸡蛋再低一点。

²把丰收的青稞煮熟了酿酒。

³把小米做的酒曲搅拌进去。

⁴在熊熊燃烧的火炉上酿造美酒。

⁵酿好的美酒接到沙黄色的酒缸里。

⁶清的美酒倒进我陶瓷的酒盅里。

⁷娶信哥哥，

⁸请你品尝一盅我亲手酿造的美酒。

⁹娶信哥哥，

¹⁰请你喝下这一盅美酒。

FIG 4. Wen Yingxian (L) and Wen Xuezhong (R) play a drinking game at the Wen ancestral graveyard (2009, Wen Xiangcheng).

SONG TWO: GATEHOUSE

1

menlou'er xiu-di gao
 门楼儿 修的 高
 gatehouse build-ASSOC high

Gatehouse built high.

2

menlou'er xiu-di gao ya
 门楼儿 修的 高 呀
 gatehouse build-ASSOC high PRT

Gatehouse built high.

3

si gezi tixuan zhe gua zai liang bian ya
 四 格子 提悬 着 挂 在 两 边 呀
 four corner overhanging thus hang at two side PRT

The four corners of the gatehouse are upturned on two sides.

4

dangzhong li gua shadeng ya
 当中 里 挂 纱灯 呀
 exactly in the center in hang up gauze lantern PRT

A gauze lantern is hung exactly in the center under the roof.

5

zuo-di shi you hu-di ren ya ai hai yo
 坐的 是 有 福的 人 呀 哎咳哟
 sit-ASSOC is has good fortune-GEN person PRT PRT

A man with good fortune lives in the house.

6

dangzhong li gua shadeng ya
 当中 里 挂 纱灯 呀
 exactly in the center in hang up gauze lantern PRT

A gauze lantern is hung exactly in the center under the roof.

7

zuo-di shi you hu-di ren ya ai hai yo
 坐的 是 有 福的 人 呀 哎咳哟
 sit-ASSOC is has good fortune-GEN person PRT PRT

A man with good fortune lives in the house.

8

dixing ma sange ren ai
 弟兄 嘛 三个 人 哎
 brothers PRT three person PRT

There are three brothers.

9

dixing ma sange ren ai
 弟兄 嘛 三个 人 哎
 brothers PRT three person PRT

There are three brothers.

10

da ya gege zuo-di shi hezhou cheng yo
 大 呀 哥哥 坐的 是 河州 城 哟
 big PRT elder brother sit-ASSOC is Hezhou City PRT

The eldest brother is the first leader of Hezhou City.¹

11

shou zhang shang xuehua'er yin ya
 手 掌 上 雪花儿 银 呀
 hand hold on snow silver PRT

He holds snow-white silver in his hands.

12

jie-di shi wenwu-di guan ya ai hai yo
 接的 是 文武的 官 呀 哎咳哟
 greet-ASSOC is civil and military-GEN officer PRT PRT

Greets civil officials and military officers.

13

shou zhang shang xuehua'er yin ya
 手 掌 上 雪花儿 银 呀
 hand hold on snow silver PRT

He holds snow-white silver in his hands.

14

jie-di shi wenwu-di guan ya ai hai yo
 接的 是 文武的 官 呀 哎咳哟
 greet-ASSOC is civil and military-GEN officer PRT PRT

Greets civil officials and military officers.

¹ In 2020, Hezhou City was known as Linxia City, Gansu Province.

15

er gege zhuangnongren ai
 二 哥哥 庄农人 哎
 second elder brother farmer PRT

The second elder brother is a farmer.

16

er gege zhuangnongren ai
 二 哥哥 庄农人 哎
 second elder brother farmer PRT

The second elder brother is a farmer.

17

xin xiang niannian yao chu yi tang men ya
 心 想 年年 要 出 一趟 门 呀
 heart think every year want go out one trip door PRT

What he wants is to leave once a year to earn money.

18

zou-liao ge zhuma cheng ya
 走了 个 zhuma 城 呀
 walk-PERF once Zhuma City PRT

He went to Zhuma City.

19

jin yin-ha na dou lier liang ya ai hai yo
 金 银下 拿 斗 俩儿 量 呀 哎咳哟
 gold silver-OBJ take *dou*¹ with measure PRT PRT

Earned so much gold and silver that he had to measure them by the *dou*.

20

zou-liao ge zhuma cheng ya
 走了 个 zhuma 城 呀
 walk-PERF once Zhuma City PRT

He went to Zhuma City.

21

jin yin-ha na dou lier liang ya ai hai yo
 金 银下 拿 斗 俩儿 量 呀 哎咳哟
 gold silver-OBJ take *dou* with measure PRT PRT

Earned so much gold and silver that he had to measure them by the *dou*.

¹ See <https://tinyurl.com/y3tukub9> (accessed 29 January 2021) for an example of a *dou* 'grain measure', which is similar to what is mentioned here.

22

san gege nianji qing ye
 三 哥哥 年纪 轻 呀
 third elder brother age young PRT

The third elder brother is young.

23

san gege nianji qing ye
 三 哥哥 年纪 轻 呀
 third elder brother age young PRT

The third elder brother is young.

24

song dao ge xuetang zhe ba ya shu-ha nian ya
 送 到 个 学堂 着 把 呀 书下 念 呀
 send arrive SG:INDEF school thus take PRT book-OBJ read PRT

He was sent to a school to study.

25

zou-liao ge beijing cheng ya
 走了 个 北京 城 呀
 walk-PERF once Beijing City PRT

He went to Beijing City to take the imperial examination.

26

zhuangyuan shi tou yi ming ya ai hai yo
 状元 是 头 一 名 呀 哎咳哟
 zhuangyuan¹ is top one place PRT PRT

Got first place and became a *zhuangyuan*.

27

zou-liao ge beijing cheng ya
 走了 个 北京 城 呀
 walk-PERF once Beijing City PRT

He went to Beijing City to take the imperial examination.

28

zhuangyuan shi tou yi ming ya ai hai yo
 状元 是 头 一 名 呀 哎咳哟
 zhuangyuan is top one place PRT PRT

Got first place and became a *zhuangyuan*.

¹ The scholar who received the highest score on highest level of the imperial examination (Hucker 1985:187).

29

yi ni ma ta xianliang ye
 一 女 嘛 她 贤良 耶
 one girl PRT she virtuous and kind PRT
 A virtuous and kind girl.

30

yi ni ma ta xianliang ye
 一 女 嘛 她 贤良 耶
 one girl PRT she virtuous and kind PRT
 A virtuous and kind girl.

31

wansuiye xuan ta zuo-liao zhenggong ya
 万岁爷 选 她 做了 正宫 呀
 emperor choose her become-PERF empress PRT
 The emperor chose her as his empress.

32

zuo-di shi jinlong dian ya
 坐的 是 金龙 殿 呀
 sit-ASSOC is Golden Dragon Palace PRT
 She sits in the Golden Dragon Palace.

33

tianxia'er-ha bao taiping ya ai hai yo
 天下儿下 保 太平 呀 哎咳哟
 the world-OBJ protect peace PRT PRT
 Keeps the world in peace.

34

zuo-di shi jinlong dian ya
 坐的 是 金龙 殿 呀
 sit-ASSOC is Golden Dragon Palace PRT
 She sits in the Golden Dragon Palace.

35

tianxia'er-ha bao taiping ya ai hai yo
 天下儿下 保 太平 呀 哎咳哟
 the world-OBJ protect peace PRT PRT
 Keeps the world in peace.

36

shou xi-li pu hongzhan ya
 首 席里 铺 红毡 呀
 first banquet table-DAT lay red felt PRT
 Place red felt under the most honorable banquet table.

37

shou xi-li pu hongzhan ya
 首 席里 铺 红毡 呀
 first banquet table-DAT lay red felt PRT

Place red felt under the most honorable banquet table.

38

man xi-li zuo-di shi babao laohan ya
 满 席里 坐的 是 八宝 老汉 呀
 all banquet table-DAT sit-ASSOC are Eight Treasures¹ old man PRT

All guests sitting around the banquet tables are Eight-Treasure elders.

39

babao laohan ya
 八宝 老汉 呀
 Eight Treasures old man PRT

Eight-Treasure elders.

40

jinyin-ha dui cheng ge shan ya ai hai yo
 金银下 堆 成 个 山 呀 哎咳哟
 gold and silver-OBJ pile become SG:INDEF hill PRT PRT

Bring so much gold and silver and pile them up into a hill.

41

babao laohan ya
 八宝 老汉 呀
 Eight Treasures old man PRT

Eight-Treasure elders.

42

jinyin-ha dui cheng ge shan ya ai hai yo
 金银下 堆 成 个 山 呀 哎咳哟
 gold and silver-OBJ pile become SG:INDEF hill PRT PRT

Bring so much gold and silver and pile them up into a hill.

ENGLISH TRANSLATION

1

¹Gatehouse built high.

²Gatehouse built high.

³The four corners of the gatehouse are upturned on two sides.

⁴A gauze lantern is hung exactly in the center under the roof.

⁵A man with good fortune lives in the house.

⁶A gauze lantern is hung exactly in the center under the roof.

⁷A man with good fortune lives in the house.

¹ For examples of the Eight Treasures, see <https://tinyurl.com/y54b6tlo> (accessed 29 January 2021).

2

⁸There are three brothers.

⁹There are three brothers.

¹⁰The eldest brother is the first leader of Hezhou City.

¹¹He holds snow-white silver in his hands.

¹²Greets civil officials and military officers.

¹³He holds snow-white silver in his hands.

¹⁴Greets civil officials and military officers.

3

¹⁵The second elder brother is a farmer.

¹⁶The second elder brother is a farmer.

¹⁷What he wants is to leave once a year to earn money.

¹⁸He went to Zhuma City.

¹⁹Earned so much gold and silver that he had to measure them by the *dou*.

²⁰He went to Zhuma City.

²¹Earned so much gold and silver that he had to measure them by the *dou*.

4

²²The third elder brother is young.

²³The third elder brother is young.

²⁴He was sent to a school to study.

²⁵He went to Beijing City to take the imperial examination.

²⁶Got first place and became a *zhuangyuan*.

²⁷He went to Beijing City to take the imperial examination.

²⁸Got first place and became a *zhuangyuan*.

5

²⁹A virtuous and kind girl.

³⁰A virtuous and kind girl.

³¹The emperor chose her as his empress.

³²She sits in the Golden Dragon Palace.

³³Keeps the world in peace.

³⁴She sits in the Golden Dragon Palace.

³⁵Keeps the world in peace.

6

³⁶Place red felt under the most honorable banquet table.

³⁷Place red felt under the most honorable banquet table.

³⁸All guests sitting around the banquet tables are Eight-Treasure elders.

³⁹Eight-Treasure elders.

⁴⁰Bring so much gold and silver and pile them up into a hill.

⁴¹Eight-Treasure elders.

⁴²Bring so much gold and silver and pile them up into a hill.

LYRICS AS PERFORMED

1

¹Men lou er xiu di gao,²Men lou er xiu di gao ya.³Si ge zi ti xuan zhe gua zai liang bian ya.⁴Dang zhong li gua sha deng ya,⁵Zuo di shi you hu di ren ya ai hai yo.⁶Dang zhong li gua sha deng ya,⁷Zuo di shi you hu di ren ya ai hai yo.

2

⁸Di xing ma san ge ren ai,⁹Di xing ma san ge ren ai.¹⁰Da ya ge ge zuo di shi he zhou cheng yo.¹¹Shou zhang shang xue hua er yin ya,¹²Jie di shi wen wu di guan ya ai hai yo.¹³Shou zhang shang xue hua er yin ya,¹⁴Jie di shi wen wu di guan ya ai hai yo.

3

¹⁵Er ge ge zhuang nong ren ai,¹⁶Er ge ge zhuang nong ren ai.¹⁷Xin xiang nian nian yao chu yi tang men ya.¹⁸Zou liao ge zhu ma cheng ya,¹⁹Jin yin ha na dou lier liang ya ai hai yo.²⁰Zou liao ge zhu ma cheng ya,²¹Jin yin ha na dou lier liang ya ai hai yo.

4

²²San ge ge nian ji qing ye,²³San ge ge nian ji qing ye.²⁴Song dao ge xue tang zhe ba ya shu ha nian ya.²⁵Zou liao ge bei jing cheng ya,²⁶Zhuang yuan shi tou yi ming ya ai hai yo.²⁷Zou liao ge bei jing cheng ya,²⁸Zhuang yuan shi tou yi ming ya ai hai yo.

5

²⁹Yi ni ma ta xian liang ye,³⁰Yi ni ma ta xian liang ye,³¹Wan sui ye xuan ta zuo liao zheng gong ya.³²Zuo di shi jin long dian ya,³³Tian xia er ha bao tai ping ya ai hai yo.³⁴Zuo di shi jin long dian ya,³⁵Tian xia er ha bao tai ping ya ai hai yo.

6

36Shou xi li pu hong zhan ya,

37Shou xi li pu hong zhan ya.

38Man xi li zuo di shi ba bao lao han ya.

39Ba bao lao han ya,

40Jin yin ha dui cheng ge shan ya ai hai yo.

41Ba bao lao han ya,

42Jin yin ha dui cheng ge shan ya ai hai yo.

LYRICS AS PERFORMED

1

1 门楼儿修的高,

2 门楼儿修的高呀。

3 四格子提悬着挂在两边呀。

4 当中里挂纱灯呀,

5 坐的是有福的人呀哎咳哟。

6 当中里挂纱灯呀,

7 坐的是有福的人呀哎咳哟。

2

8 弟兄嘛三个人哎,

9 弟兄嘛三个人哎。

10 大呀哥哥坐的是河州城哟。

11 手掌上雪花儿银呀,

12 接的是文武的官呀哎咳哟。

13 手掌上雪花儿银呀,

14 接的是文武的官呀哎咳哟。

3

15 二哥哥庄农人哎,

16 二哥哥庄农人哎。

17 心想年年要出一趟门呀。

18 走了个 zhuma 城呀,

19 金银哈拿斗俩儿量呀哎咳哟。

20 走了个 zhuma 城呀,

21 金银哈拿斗俩儿量呀哎咳哟。

4

22 三哥哥年纪轻耶,

23 三哥哥年纪轻耶。

24 送到个学堂着把呀书哈念呀。

25 走了个北京城呀,

26 状元是头一名呀哎咳哟。

27 走了个北京城呀,

28 状元是头一名呀哎咳哟。

5

- 29 一女嘛她贤良耶,
 30 一女嘛她贤良耶。
 31 万岁爷选她做了正宫呀。
 32 坐的是金龙殿呀,
 33 天下儿哈保太平呀哎咳哟。
 34 坐的是金龙殿呀,
 35 天下儿哈保太平呀哎咳哟。

6

- 36 首席里铺红毡呀,
 37 首席里铺红毡呀。
 38 满席里坐的是八宝老汉呀。
 39 八宝老汉呀,
 40 金银哈堆成个山呀哎咳哟。
 41 八宝老汉呀,
 42 金银哈堆成个山呀哎咳哟。

LYRICS IN MSC PINYIN

1

- ¹Men lou er xiu de gao,
²Men lou er xiu de gao.
³Si jiao gao xuan gua zai liang bian.
⁴Zheng zhong jian gua zhe yi zhan sha deng,
⁵Fang zi li zhu de shi yi wei you fu qi de ren.
⁶Zheng zhong jian gua zhe yi zhan sha deng,
⁷Fang zi li zhu de shi yi wei you fu qi de ren.

2

- ⁸Di xiong san ge ren,
⁹Di xiong san ge ren.
¹⁰Da ge zai he zhou cheng zuo guan.
¹¹Shou shang peng zhe xue hua yin,
¹²Ying jie wen wu guan yuan.
¹³Shou shang peng zhe xue hua yin,
¹⁴Ying jie wen wu guan yuan.

3

- ¹⁵Er ge shi ge nong min,
¹⁶Er ge shi ge nong min.
¹⁷Ta xin xiang mei nian dou chu men zhuan qian.
¹⁸Ta qu le yi tang zhu ma cheng,
¹⁹Zhuan qu de jin yin duo dao yong dou sheng lai liang.
²⁰Ta qu le yi tang zhu ma cheng,
²¹Zhuan qu de jin yin duo dao yong dou sheng lai liang.

4

²²San ge nian ji hen qing,²³San ge nian ji hen qing.²⁴Ta bei song dao xue tang qu du shu.²⁵Qu bei jing can jia ke ju kao shi,²⁶Ta kao qu le zhuang yuan.²⁷Qu bei jing can jia ke ju kao shi,²⁸Ta kao qu le zhuang yuan.

5

²⁹Hai you yi ge xian hui shan liang de nü er,³⁰Hai you yi ge xian hui shan liang de nü er.³¹Huang di xuan ta zuo le zheng gong niang niang.³²Ta zuo zai jin long dian,³³Wei tian xia bai xing bao tai ping.³⁴Ta zuo zai jin long dian,³⁵Wei tian xia bai xing bao tai ping.

6

³⁶Shou xi zhuo zi di xia pu zhe hong zhan,³⁷Shou xi zhuo zi di xia pu zhe hong zhan.³⁸Suo you xi shang zuo zhe de dou shi ba bao lao han.³⁹Ba bao lao han men,⁴⁰Dai lai de jin yin cai bao dui cheng le shan.⁴¹Ba bao lao han men,⁴²Dai lai de jin yin cai bao dui cheng le shan.

LYRICS IN MSC CHARACTERS

1

¹门楼儿修的高,²门楼儿修的高。³四角高悬挂在两边。⁴正中间挂着一盏纱灯,⁵房子里住的是一位有福气的人。⁶正中间挂着一盏纱灯,⁷房子里住的是一位有福气的人。

2

⁸弟兄三个人,⁹弟兄三个人。¹⁰大哥在河州城做官。¹¹手上捧着雪花银,¹²迎接文武官员。¹³手上捧着雪花银,¹⁴迎接文武官员。

3

15 二哥是个农民,

16 二哥是个农民。

17 他心想每年都出门赚钱。

18 他去了一趟 zhuma 城,

19 赚取的金银多到用斗升来量。

20 他去了一趟 zhuma 城,

21 赚取的金银多到用斗升来量。

4

22 三哥年纪很轻,

23 三哥年纪很轻。

24 他被送到学堂去读书。

25 去北京参加科举考试,

26 他考取了状元。

27 去北京参加科举考试,

28 他考取了状元。

5

29 还有一个贤惠善良的女儿,

30 还有一个贤惠善良的女儿。

31 皇帝选她做了正宫娘娘。

32 她坐在金龙殿,

33 为天下百姓保太平。

34 她坐在金龙殿,

35 为天下百姓保太平。

6

36 首席桌子底下铺着红毡,

37 首席桌子底下铺着红毡。

38 所有席上坐着的都是八宝老汉。

39 八宝老汉们,

40 带来的金银财宝堆成了山。

41 八宝老汉们,

42 带来的金银财宝堆成了山。

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NON-ENGLISH TERMS

<i>babao</i> 八宝	Jishishan 积石山	Tu 土
Bao Yizhi 鲍义志	<i>laohan</i> 老汉	Wen Jinde 文进德
Bao'an 保安	Linxia 临夏	Wen Xiangcheng 文祥呈
Beijing 北京	<i>luzi</i> 炉子	Wen Xuezhong 文学忠
Dahejia 大河家	<i>menlou</i> 门楼	Wen Yingxian 文英先
Deng Yulong 邓玉龙	Minhe 民和	Wenjia 文家
Dengjia 邓家	Qinghai 青海	<i>Wuyan de Niujiaohao</i> 呜咽 的牛角号
dmag sgar དམག་སྐར་	Renjia 任家	Xing'er 杏儿
Dongxiang 东乡	Salar, Sala 撒拉	<i>xuetang</i> 学堂
Gansu 甘肃	Sanchuan 三川	Yindong 银洞
Guanting 官亭	<i>shadeng</i> 纱灯	<i>zhenggong</i> 正宫
Haidong 海东	<i>shazi</i> 沙子	Zhu Lanxiang 朱兰香
Han 汉	<i>shouxi</i> 首席	<i>zhuangyuan</i> 状元
Hezhou 河州	skal bzang nor bu སྐལ་བཟང་ནོར་བུ་	Ziger, sgar སྐར་
Hui 回	ཚོ་བུ།	
<i>jidan</i> 鸡蛋	<i>taiping</i> 太平	